

Effect of Financial Performance on Environmental Reporting Practices of Listed Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

Effect of financial performance on environmental reporting practices by firms on a global basis has been a long standing issue and previous results remain controversial because of the mixed results. Consequently, this study assesses the effect of financial performance on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study has a population of sixty-one (61) manufacturing firms and a sample size of 45 firms which was arrived at based on a criterion that the listed manufacturing firms with full data over the period of the study are considered. Data are collected from annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms through content analysis and the data was analysed using multiple regression technique, descriptive statistics, variance inflation factor and correlation analysis. The study found that the four measures of financial performance examined, namely; return on assets, return on equity, net profit margin, earnings per share and control variable of firm size have no statistical significant effect on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study also found that the control variable of firm age had positive and significant effect on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study recommends, based on the findings, that listed manufacturing firms in financial difficulty in Nigeria should be granted incentives such as tax holiday and guaranteed bank loans to ensure that manufacturing firms in Nigeria live longer in terms of age which encourages environmental reporting practices. It also recommends that ISO14031 reporting guideline should be made mandatory as a reporting guideline among listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria, in order to boost their environmental reporting practices and to enhance uniformity in reporting practices for easy comparison among firms.

Keywords: Environmental Reporting Practices, Financial performance, Manufacturing Firms

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1. Introduction.

Environmental reporting practices involves release of information on the impact of organizations' activities on the natural environment and such activities include, waste management, recycling, carbon management, emission and pollution management, tree planting and wildlife conservation among others. There has been an increasing need for information by various stakeholders through annual reports and accounts of listed firms on the issue of sustainability. Sustainability has become a major component of today's business activities because of increased stakeholder awareness on growing sustainable business development by increasing financial resources towards protecting the environment in which the business

operates. This therefore makes stakeholders to demand for more information from companies thereby encouraging listed firms to actively participate in environmental reporting (KPMG 2012).

Profit is used as an index to measure corporate performance of resources put in place because it measures the net effectiveness and soundness of business efforts and an ultimate test of business performance since the major objective of a business is to make profit (Okoli, 2006). It is the risk premium that covers the cost of staying in a business, replacement of obsolete assets, market risk and uncertainty. The distinction between profitability and profit lies in the fact that profitability can be judged from the net return as well as the cost saving of alternative transactions. In the concept of profitability, it is enough that a company knows that it is making profit. It also needs to know if it is making as much profit as it could because management is always looking at possible cost reduction measures and net return improvement through either increase in sales of production or production mix to maximize profit. This cost saving efforts by management of manufacturing firms may manifest in not being environmentally friendly in terms of allocating financial resources to protect the environment where the firm operates in order to maximize profit for its shareholders. In Nigeria, Iyoha (2010) argues that the concern of organizations is profit making and dividend payment and as such lesser attention is given to environmental matters. Thus, the little or no concern for the management of by-products and after effects of industrial activities in Nigeria triggered the establishment of the Federal Ministry of Environment (formerly Federal Environmental Protection Agency) and the National Environmental Standards and Regulatory Enforcement Agency (NESREA) in order to ensure that industrial activities do not negatively impact on the environment by initiating control measures.

Though in Nigeria, environmental reporting issues remain voluntary in line with global best practices but some countries like Finland and Sweden have made it compulsory. As a result of the voluntary nature of environmental reporting there are major differences in terms of quality and quantity of environmental information reported by entities within the same country and in different countries. These differences in the extent of disclosure among countries is due to lack of a uniform standard regulating environmental reporting practices on a global scale. The analysis of International Accounting Standard (IAS) and International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) show that no international standard is exclusively dedicated to the provisions of such information but there are numerous direct and indirect remarks on the issue of environmental accounting in the different accounting standards (Goyal, 2013). As a result of this, one of the most widely known international standards for assessing environmental activity of firms is the International Organization for Standardisation (ISO) 14031 disclosure requirements which provides voluntary standards of environmental reporting. Uwigbe (2011) opines that (ISO) 14031 provides sustainability standards capable of monitoring long-time corporate growth, efficiency, performance, competitiveness by incorporating economic and environmental issues into corporate management when it is used as a standard benchmark for reporting.

Studies on effect of financial performance on environmental reporting practices have been conducted by many researchers but very limited in the context of Nigeria. In Nigeria, few studies

have considered the effect of financial performance on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms. For example, Uwigbe (2011) examines the effect of profit on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria over the period 2005-2009 with a sample size of 30 firms using return on assets. Similarly, Bassey, Effiok and Etom (2013) investigate the effect of profit on environmental reporting practices of non-listed oil producing firms in Nigeria over the period 2008-2010 using return on assets. Despite these efforts, there is rarely any empirical study on effect of financial performance on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria, that covered a period of seventeen (17) years. Besides, none of these studies examined return on equity which Pandey (2005) considers as the most important ratio in financial analysis.

The objective of this study therefore, is to assess the effect of financial performance on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria based on ISO 14031 checklist.

In order to achieve the objective of the study, the following hypotheses are formulated in null forms

- i. Return on assets has no significant effect on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
- ii. Return on equity has no significant effect on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
- iii. Net profit margin has no significant effect on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
- iv. Earnings per share has no significant effect on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

The scope of the study covers the period 2000-2016. This period was chosen because it saw the increasing awareness on issues of environmental sustainability requiring firms to engage in environmental reporting even though on a voluntary basis. The choice of manufacturing firms (including oil and gas) is that by their mode of operations they are more prone to environmental.

2. Literature Review

Henderson and Peirson (2004) suggests that environmental reports by firms cover sustainability efforts made by firms in a manner that reflect concerns about environmental protection, intergenerational equality, the protection of the earth and its resources. Furthermore, Gray, Kouhy and Lavers (1995) define corporate environmental reporting as the process of communicating the environmental effects of organizations' economic action to particular interest groups within society and to society at large, thereby influencing the public's perception towards their operations. Similarly, Gray *et al.* (1995) opine that companies use their environmental reports to construct themselves and their relationships with others as they strive to create and maintain the conditions for their continued profitability and growth. Environmental report helps them to rationalize and justify the corporate entity not merely describing effective management, but legitimizing corporate power and maintaining confidence of the public. Based on these concepts of environmental reporting, it is clear that the advocates of environmental reporting are

convinced that reporting is a crucial lever for change in the direction of improved environmental performance and in the longer term bring about eco-efficiency and sustainability.

Financial performance as a concept is the general measure of how well a firm uses its resources to generate profits. It is usually measured using accounting measures of profitability such as return on assets and return on equity. A company should earn profits in order to survive and grow over a long period of time (Pandey, 2005). Profits are essential but it would be wrong to assume that every action initiated by a corporation should aim at profit maximization to the detriment of environment, employees and society (Pandey, 2005). Epps and Cereola (2008) state that the operating performance of a business organization can be measured using Return on Asset (ROA) which shows the amount of earnings generated from the resources owned by them. On the other hand, the ROE shows how much earnings are generated from the investment of shareholders in the equity of a business organization. Return on Equity (ROE) measure is used to evaluate the financial performance of a firm. Return on Equity measures the return earned on the common stockholders' investment in the firm (Gitman, 2007). The higher the return the better off are the owners. Pandey (2005) opines that the ROE is the most important ratio in financial analysis because earning of a satisfactory return is the most desirable objective of a business and the ratio of the net profit to owner's equity reflects the extent to which this objective has been accomplished. This ratio is of great importance to present as well as future shareholders and to management whose core duty is maximizing owners' wealth because without profits, a firm could not attract outside capital and investors (Gitman, 2007).

Deegan, (2002) states that, legitimacy theory hypothesize that companies are bound to an unwritten social contract within the society where they operate. Failure to comply with their legitimacy will threaten the companies' performances and survival. Therefore, more profitable companies can be expected to disclose more voluntary social and environmental information than non-profitable companies. Corporate financial performance is used by a number of studies as an explanatory variable for differences in environmental disclosure level. However, the relationship between corporate financial performance and corporate environmental disclosure is arguably one of the most controversial issues yet to be resolved because of mixed results that have been found (Choi, 1998).

Wiseman (1982) examines the relationship between the annual reports of 26 firms covering the period 1980-1981 in three industries with their financial and environmental performances using the ISO 14031 environmental reporting guideline. Content analysis was used to measure the extent of disclosures using 60 disclosure items to evaluate the quality and accuracy of environmental disclosures. The performance indicators used in the analysis of the level of financial performance of the selected firms included; earnings per share, price-earnings ratio and dividend yield. Regression analysis is used to estimate the model and the findings indicate that the voluntary environmental reports were incomplete, providing inadequate disclosure for most of the environmental performance items included in the disclosure items. The findings also disclosed that no relationship exists between the contents of the firms' environmental disclosures and the firms' financial performance. Freedman and Jaggi (1988) investigate the association

between environmental disclosures and the financial performance of firms in four highly polluting industries. The results indicate that there was no association between environmental disclosures and financial performance.

In addition, Hannifa and Cooke (2002) investigate the impact of profit and corporate governance on environmental disclosure in listed Malaysian firms. Using a sample of 226 listed firms over the period 1999-2000, the data was analysed using ordinary least square regression and It was found that there was a significant positive association between the level of environmental disclosure and return on assets (ROA) of the firm. They observed that the economic performance of a firm is considered as an important factor in determining whether environmental issues will be a priority or not. This is because in periods of low economic performance, the firm's economic objectives may be given more attention than environmental concerns.

In China, Fan (2006) examines the determinants of environmental disclosure among Chinese firms, over the period 2000-2004. Data was obtained from a sample of 226 firms listed in Malaysia and analysed using multiple linear regression. It reports that profitability has a significant impact on voluntary environmental disclosure. On the contrary in a study of accounting guidelines for environmental issues by Smith (2007), the study applies data of 6 years (2001-2005) using a sample of 148 firms. The data is analysed using ordinary least square regression analysis and finds a significant inverse relationship between environmental disclosure and the return on assets of firms in the Malaysian context.

Furthermore, the impact of environmental accounting and reporting on financial performance of selected oil and gas companies in Niger-Delta region of Nigeria was examined by Bassey, Effiok and Eton (2013). Data was analysed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient after a sample of 30 non-listed firms was arrived at using random and stratified sampling techniques. Data are gathered from primary and secondary sources covering the period 2008-2010. It finds that the level of environmental disclosure had positive and insignificant association with firm's return on assets (ROA).

Thus, from the literature reviewed on various scholars in different countries, it is clear that more profitable firms are likely to disclose more environmental information while less profitable firms tend to be more secretive and conservative in terms of environmental disclosure.

Dragomir (2009) investigates financial performance and environmentally sensitive disclosure in a European setting. Using a sample size of sixty (60) largest European Union industrial business groups for the year 2008. Content analysis is used in collecting data by being transformed from qualitative to quantitative information. It finds that there is positive and insignificant relationship between financial performance proxied by ROE and environmental reporting practices of large European firms.

Gibson, Collins and Cosmas (2013) conduct a study on firm financial performance and environmental reporting practices of South African listed firms using a sample of nine (9) mining

firms for the year 2011. It collects data using content analysis technique and the findings show that there is no significant relationship between the variables and environmental reporting practices in South Africa. The limitations of this study is that it uses only nine firms for just one (1) year. The result may change if more firms are used.

Similarly in Malaysia, Tse, Teh and Ang (2014) examine the impact of financial performance on environmental improvement of leading listed companies using a sample of 78 firms. It uses content analysis in collecting the data and it is analysed using multiple regression technique. It finds a positive and significant impact between financial performance of ROE and environmental reporting practices for the period 2008-2012 which is the period of the study.

Similarly, Kasbun, Teh, and Ong (2016) examines the effect of financial performance and environmental reporting practices of Malaysian listed firms over the period 2006-2013. Content analysis is used through word count for data collection from a sample of 200 firms. It finds after multiple regression analysis that Return On Equity (ROE) has a positive and significant effect on environmental reporting practices. This study suffers from the limitation of scope of the study being only seven years, consequently the results of the study may change if the scope increases.

In Kenya, Karambu and Joseph (2016) investigates the effect of financial performance on environmental disclosure of listed firms at Nairobi Stock Exchange. It collects data from a sample of 32 firms which it analysed using regression. It finds a positive and insignificant relationship between ROE and environmental reporting practices. From the literatures reviewed, there is mixed finding on the effect of financial performance on environmental reporting practices of firms both in developed and developing countries, hence there is need for further research on the effect of ROE and environmental reporting practices.

Under legitimacy theory, firms' continued existence depends on the acceptance of the society where they operate. Since the firms can be influenced by the society, legitimacy is assumed to be an important resource determining their survival (Deegan, 2002). The theory suggests that larger firms are more likely to come under public scrutiny and are expected to have more influence on general business environment. A number of studies over the past decades have tested the influence of firm size on the level of environmental disclosure. Most studies report a positive relationship between company size and the extent of environmental disclosure in both developing and developed countries (Ahmed & Nicholls 1994; Hossain, Islan & Andrew, 2006). For example, findings by Mohammed and Tamoi (2006) show that company's size as measured by log of total assets provides an explanation on the variability of environmental report among Malaysian companies.

In Greece, Galvani, Graves and Stavropoulos (2011) examine the extent to which Greek companies implement a set of environmental accounting practices and the data was analysed using estimated multiple linear regression model, the relationship between various firm characteristics and environmental disclosures are examined. 100 listed firms are selected for the study and a disclosure index is constructed which consists of 15 items of information in order to

identify the factors that may have a significant influence on the disclosure level of environmental information by the firms. The results of the study show that there is a positive relationship between corporate size and the disclosure of environmental information in annual reports of 2009. Thus, from the foregoing reviews firm size has a great impact on environmental reporting practices because the larger the firm the more the tendency it impacts on the environment in the pursuit of economic activities. Also Based on the legitimacy theory, it is expected that large firms will disclose more social and environmental information than smaller firms because the society expects more environmental concern from them.

Makori and Jogonga (2013) examined if there is any significant relationship between environmental reporting and profitability of selected firms listed in India. The data for the study were collected from annual reports and accounts of 14 randomly selected quoted companies in Bombay Stock Exchange for the year 2007. The data were analysed using Multiple Regression Models and the findings showed that there was a significant negative relationship between environmental accounting and Return On Capital Employed (ROCE) and Earnings Per Share (EPS) while on the other hand a significant and positive relationship was found between environmental accounting and Net Profit Margin (NPM) and Divided Per Share (DPS).

Firm age under the legitimacy theory posits that companies' societal existence depends on the acceptance of the society where they operate. Since the companies can be influenced by the society, legitimacy is assumed an important resource determining their survival (Deegan, 2002). Therefore, older companies with longer societal existence may have taken relatively more legitimacy and may have a higher reputation and involvement of social responsibility than younger companies. As a company operates longer in terms of age, there will be more communication needed with the outside community. This provides companies with wide social networks, affecting their public images (Yang, 2009). Previous studies support the significant association between age of firm and environmental information disclosure (Yang, 2009). Omar (2014) examine the determinants of corporate Social and environmental disclosure in Bahrain using data of 2012 which was obtained from a sample of 33 listed firms and was analysed using multiple linear regression and it reports that age had no significant impact on voluntary environmental disclosure. Based on the above reviews, there is mixed findings as to whether the more a firm advances in age the more likely the company would disclose social and environmental information because of the mixed findings.

A number of different theories have been used to explain why corporations might voluntarily disclose social and environmental information to outside parties. According to Gray et al. (1995) the theories that seem to have been most successful in explaining the content and the level of social and environmental information disclosures are the legitimacy theory and the stakeholder theory. Hooghiemstra (2000) states that under legitimacy and stakeholder theories, social and environmental disclosure is used in order to guard corporations' reputation and identity. However, Guthrie and Parker (1990) states that, legitimacy theory is one of the most adopted theories for explaining corporate social and environmental disclosures. Perrow (1970) as cited in Omar (2014) defines legitimacy as a generalized perception or assumption that the actions of an

entity are desirable, proper, or appropriate within some socially constructed system of norms, value, beliefs, and definitions.

In contrast to agency theory, the legitimacy theory provides a more comprehensive viewpoint on corporate social disclosure as it clearly recognizes that organizations are bound by the social contract in which they agree to perform various socially desired actions in return for approval of their objectives, which guarantees their continued existence and their successful operations (Guthrie and Parker, 1989; Brown and Deegan, 1998; Deegan, 2002;). From the foregoing theoretical review, Legitimacy theory suggests a relationship between corporate environmental disclosure and community concerns so that management must react to community expectations and changes. Therefore, this study is anchored on the legitimacy theory because management must react to environmental issues concerning the environment they operate to gain acceptance of the society and survival of their firm.

3. Methodology

This is a longitudinal panel data study and the population is all the sixty-one (61) listed manufacturing firms operating and trading on the floor of Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) as at 31st December 2016 from which a sample of 45 firms are drawn based on a criterion where all the manufacturing firms that met it has a chance of being selected. The criterion is that the listed manufacturing firm must have full data over the period of the study (2000-2016).

A dichotomous procedure of content analysis technique of gathering data is used in codifying qualitative information into categories in order to derive quantitative values. Any of the sampled firm selected could score a maximum of sixty (60) points and a minimum of 0. The formula for calculating the reporting score using the sixty (60) disclosure index items in ISO 14031 benchmark as adopted from previous studies (Wiseman 1982; Deegan and Gordon, 1996; Hackston and Milne, 1996;Uwigbe 2011) is shown below.

$$RS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{60} r_i}{60}$$

Where:

RS = Reporting score r_i = a score of (1) if the item is reported and (0) if not reported.

$i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 60$. All the reported scores are then summed up and divided by 60 to arrive at a value greater than zero (0) for the dependent variable.

For the purpose of finding the effect of return on assets return on equity, net profit margin and earnings per share as independent variables on environmental reporting practices as the dependent variable a multiple regression analysis is adopted. The functional relationship is given as follows.

$$Erp=f(roa, roe, npm, eps) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Since it is believed there are other variables that can also influence environmental reporting practices of firms, firm size and firm age are introduced as control variables of the study.

$$Hence \text{erp}=f(roa, roe, npm, eps, fsz, age) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

With the aid of the second equation the study arrives at a model which is presented as follows:

$$Erp_{i,t} = a + \beta_1 roai_{i,t} + \beta_2 roei_{i,t} + \beta_3 npmi_{i,t} + \beta_4 epsi_{i,t} + \beta_5 fszi_{i,t} + \beta_6 agei_{i,t} + U_{i,t}, \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where Erp=Environmental reporting practices and is measured by unweighted disclosure approach and a firm is scored “1” for an item disclosed in the annual report and “0” if it is not reported. All the reported scores are then summed up and divided by 60 (sixty) to give a value for environmental report. ROA=Return on Assets and is measured by dividing profit after tax by total assets at the end of the year as used by Hannifa and Cooke (2002). ROE=Return on Equity is measured by dividing profit after tax by total equity of the firm at the end of each year as measured by Karambu and Joseph (2016). NPM= Net Profit Margin is measured as profit after tax divided by turnover (total sales) for the year as used by Makori and Jagonga (2013). EPS= Earnings Per Share is measured by total earnings divided by total number of shares in issue at year end as used by Makori and Jagonga (2013). Fsz=Firm Size and is measured by natural log of assets at the end of the year as measured by Mohammed and Tamoi (2012). Firm Age is measured as the number of years after the firm was first listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as used by Omar (2014). a is the intercept, β_{1-4} is the coefficient of the independent variables and β_{5-6} is the coefficient of control variables.

The following diagnostic tests are conducted to enrich the analysis of data

- i. Data normality test was conducted using shapiro-wilk W test for normal data
- ii. Multicollinearity test, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance values are conducted to ensure that some or all of the explanatory variables in a multiple regression analysis are not highly inter-correlated to cause multicollinearity problems in the data
- iii. Heteroscedasticity test is conducted to check whether the variability of error terms is constant or not.
- iv. Hausman specification test is conducted to enable the study choose between fixed and random effects

4. Results and Discussion

Table 4.1 shows the summary descriptive statistics of the dependent and independent variables in terms of the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values. Erp, has a mean of 23.9% with a standard deviation of 10.6%, a minimum of 12% and a maximum of 60% suggesting that there is a wide dispersion in environmental disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The implication is that listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria have differences in the quantity and quality of environmental information disclosed.

Table 4.1 Descriptive statistics of variables

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Erp	765	0.239	0.106	0.12	0.6
Roa	765	0.126	0.481	-0.56	8.44
Roe	765	0.339	1.158	-21.73	15.60
Npm	765	0.110	0.244	-4.27	2.36
Eps	765	2.881	4.865	-20.76	43.58
Fsz	765	9.567	1.741	3.06	14.24
Age	765	26.202	9.457	1	51

Source: STATA 14 Output 2017

Return on Assets (Roa) has a mean of 0.126 with a standard deviation of 0.481, a minimum and maximum values of -0.59 and 8.44 respectively. This suggests a wide dispersion in Roa of manufacturing firms because some of the firms are more profitable than others. Also Return on Equity (Roe) has a mean and standard deviation values of 0.339 and 1.158 respectively, implying that on the average there is much differences in Roe among listed manufacturing firms in Nigerian because there is a wide dispersion in its values of mean and standard deviation. This also confirms the results of Roa. The maximum Roe was 15.60 indicating that some of the listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria had high Roe compared to the mean. Furthermore, net profit margin had a mean of 0.110 and standard deviation of 0.244 which also indicates a wide dispersion in net profit margin of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. On the other hand, earnings per share had a mean of 2.881 and standard deviation of 4.865 which shows that listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria have similar nature of dividend payment because there is no wide dispersion between the mean and its standard deviation.

Firm size (Fsz) had a mean value of 9.567 and standard deviation value of 1.741 which shows a very wide dispersion and this may be due to the fact listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria vary in sizes because some of the firms are very large compared to others in terms of assets. Considering firm age, the average age of the manufacturing firms is 25 years while the youngest is 1 year and the oldest is 51 years. The standard deviation of the firm ages is 9.457 suggesting a wide dispersion of the firm ages of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria because some of the firms are very young compared to others that are much older.

The correlation between the dependent and independent variables are presented in table 4.2 and it is evident from the table that the magnitude of the correlation amongst the explanatory variables generally indicates no severe multicollinearity problems in the study because the highest correlation coefficient is 0.7165 between Roa and Roe. Hussain, Islam and Andrew (2006) suggest that that multicollinearity may be a problem when the correlation between independent variables is 0.9 and above where as Emory (1982) considers more than 0.80 to be problematic.

Table 4.2 Correlation Matrix of Dependent and Independent variables

Variables	Erp	Roa	Roe	Npm	Eps	Fsz	Age	Vif
Erp	1.000							
Roa	0.08	1.000						2.13
Roe	0.019	0.7165	1.000					2.43
Npm	0.044	0.452	0.563	1.000				1.52
Eps	0.138	0.027	0.134	0.073	1.000			1.13
Fsz	0.456	-0.068	-0.022	0.073	0.244	1.000		1.09
Age	0.376	0.051	-0.039	-0.099	0.113	0.217	1.000	1.07

Source: STATA 14 Output 2017

To determine the presence of collinearity problem, a Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test is carried out and the results provide evidence of the absence of collinearity because the results of the VIF test range from a minimum of 1.07 to a maximum of 2.43 and a mean of 1.56. VIF of 5.00 can still be a proof of absence of collinearity (Neter, Kutner, Nachtsheim & Wasserman

1996) Also, the test of heteroscedasticity was conducted to check whether the variability of error terms is constant or not. The presence of heteroscedasticity usually signifies that the variation of the residuals or error term is not constant and this could affect inferences in respect of beta coefficient, coefficient of determination (R^2) and F-statistic of the study. The result of the test reveals that there is presence of heteroscedasticity because the probability of the chi square is statistically significant at 1% with value of 69.17 and p- value of 0.000. This further necessitated the study to run for fixed effect regression and random effect regression models. The use of regression model to estimate the coefficient of any panel data requires the determination of whether the fixed effect or the random effect model suits the data more efficiently using Hausman statistical test (Gujerati, Porter & Gunasekar 2012). The results of the Hausman specification test shows that the fixed effect is more appropriate for the study with a chisquare value of 89.22 and p value of 0.000.

The Shapiro Wilks W test for normal data was conducted and it showed that the data for the study was not normally distributed because all the variables of the study had a significant p-value of less than 1% hence the robust standard error fixed effect model was used in discussing the results

The regression results of Fixed Effects (FE) of the dependent variable environmental reporting practices (Erp) and the independent variables of return on assets (roa), return on equity (roe), net profit margin (Npm), earnings per share (eps), firm size (fsz), and firm age (Age) are presented in table 4.3

Table 4.3 Regression Results (Fixed Effects)

Ind. Variables	Coefficients	Robust Std Error	T Statistics	P-Values
Constants	-0.0046	0.0338	-0.14	0.893
Roa	-0.0029	0.0059	-0.50	0.620
Roe	0.0004	0.0024	0.2	0.839
Npm	0.0121	0.0143	0.84	0.403
Eps	-0.0003	0.0010	-0.34	0.739
Fsz	-0.0014	0.0032	-0.44	0.659
Age	0.0098	0.0014	6.94	0.000
No of Obs	765	765	765	765
Het Test	69.17(0.0000)			
R-Squared (Within)	0.4426			
F-Statistic	14.79 (0.0000)			
Hausman	89.22 (0.0000)			

Source: STATA 14 Outputs 2017 based on study data appendix A

From the p-values which is statistically significant, the validity of the model under the fixed effect estimations is evident. The R-squared of 44.26% for the fixed effect shows that the changes in environmental reporting practices is substantially accounted for by the explanatory variables. This implies that the independent variables can explain 44.26% of the changes in the

dependent variable. Furthermore, the fixed effect estimation shows, the F-statistics of 14.79 and p-value of 0.000 which confirm the fitness of the model.

In the fixed effect (FE) return on assets has negative coefficient of -0.0029 and a p-value of 0.620. From table 4.3, the probability value of 0.620% is more than 0.05% level of significance ($0.620\% > 0.05\%$) and based on this finding the study fails to reject the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant effect of return on assets on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The implication of this is that as return on assets decreases the level of environmental reporting practices also decreases but it is not significant. This finding supports the studies conducted by Bassy, Effiok and Etom (2013) who document that there is no significant relationship between environmental reporting practices and return on assets. This finding also supports legitimacy theory which posits that the management of firms try to meet the needs of stakeholders such as environmental reporting when profits are made to gain acceptance because legitimacy is assumed an important resource determining the survival of the firms.

It opposes that of Hannifa and Cooke (2002) and Fan (2006) who found that there is a significant relationship between environmental reporting and return on assets of non-listed petroleum firms in Nigeria. The implication of this to investors that are environmentally friendly is to encourage growth in profitability of the firms they are interested in to enhance the ability of the firms to carry out sustainability activities.

Furthermore, the robust standard error fixed effect estimates that return on equity is positive and insignificantly related to environmental reporting practice of Nigeria listed manufacturing firms with coefficients and p-values of 0.0004 and 0.839 respectively. From table 4.3, the probability value of 0.839% is more than 0.05% level of significance ($0.839\% > 0.05\%$) and based on this finding the study fails to reject the null hypothesis which states there is no significant effect of return on assets on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This implies that return on equity has no significant effect on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigerian. This finding also implies that as return on equity of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria improved environmental reporting practices also increased but it is not significant. This finding confirms those of Dragomir (2009) who found positive and insignificant relationship between return on equity and environmental reporting practices. This finding also supports legitimacy theory which posits that the management of firms try to meet the needs of stakeholders such as environmental reporting when profits are made to gain acceptance because legitimacy is assumed an important resource determining the survival of the firms. However, this finding is not consistent with that of Tse, Teh and Ang (2014) and Kasbun Teh and Ong (2016) who found a significant effect of roe on environmental reporting practices.

In addition, Fixed Effect (FE) shows a positive coefficient of 0.0121 and a p value of 0.403 for Net profit margin. Table 4.3 shows the probability value of 0.403% to be more than 0.05% level of significance ($0.403\% > 0.05\%$) and based on this finding the study fails to reject the null hypothesis which states that net profit margin has no significant effect on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The implication of this finding is that as the net profit margin of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria increases the level of

environmental reporting practices also increases. This finding contradicts those of Makori and Jagonga (2013) who document that net profit margin has a positive and significant effect on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in India.

Earnings per share (EPS) was estimated to have a negative coefficient of 0.0003 with a p-value of 0.739 indicating that as it decreases, the level of environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria also decreased but it is not significant. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant effect of earnings per share on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria is not rejected because the probability value of 0.739% is more than 0.05% level of significance ($0.739\% > 0.05\%$). This finding is not in tandem the study of Makori and Jagonga (2013) who found a significant positive effect of earnings per share on environmental reporting practices in India.

Similarly, considering firm size the Fixed effect (FE) shows that firm size is insignificant and negatively related to environmental reporting practice of Nigeria listed manufacturing firms at 1% confidence level with coefficients and p-values of 0.0014 and 0.659 respectively. Table 4.3, shows that the probability value of 0.659% is more than 0.05% level of significance ($0.659\% > 0.05\%$) and based on this finding the study fails to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that as firm size decreases, its level of environmental reporting practices also decreases but it is not significant. This finding supports those of Mohammed and Tamoi (2006); Galvani, Graves and Stavropoulos (2011) who found a positive and significant effect of firm size on environmental reporting practices.

Considering firm age, the Fixed Effect (FE) show a positive coefficient of 0.001 and a p value of 0.000 as table 4.3 shows that the probability value of 0.000% is less than 0.05% level of significance ($0.000\% < 0.05\%$) and based on this finding the study rejects the null hypothesis. This implies that as the age of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria increase the level of environmental reporting correspondingly increases. This finding is in line with legitimacy theory which posits that as a company operates over time, there will be more communication needed to the outside community. This provides companies with wide social networks, affecting their public image. This finding opposes that of Omar (2014) who documented that there is no association between firm age and the level of environmental reporting practices.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations.

This study examines effect of financial performance on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria over the period of seventeen years (2000-2016). The study covered forty-five listed manufacturing firms out of the sixty-one firms operating in Nigeria. The findings have a clear policy implication on environmental reporting practices in Nigeria based on the results of the descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, the OLS and the fixed effects of the study. The study concludes that the four measures of financial performance examined by study, namely; return on assets, return on equity, net profit margin earnings per share and control variable of firm size have no statistical significant effect on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Furthermore, the study concludes that the control variable of firm age had positive and significant effect on environmental reporting practices of listed

manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study recommends, based on the findings, that listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria should be granted incentives such as tax holiday by government and banks to enhance their continuous operation. This can make the manufacturing firms in Nigeria live longer in terms of age which encourages environmental reporting practices. Furthermore, government should no longer allow environmental reporting to be voluntary but make it compulsory using ISO 14031 reporting guidelines as a common standard of reporting among the management of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This will serve the purpose of having a detailed environmental reporting information and easy comparison of such information between firms in similar industries.

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